

Short communication

The silent sex-related burden of human exposure to arctic dietary pollution

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ABSTRACT

Climate change is accelerating the release and redistribution of contaminants in the Arctic, increasing human exposure to both legacy and emerging pollutants. Arctic biomonitoring studies reveal consistently higher contaminant levels in men than in women, driven by distinct dietary habits, exposure pathways, and physiological processes. To ensure effective protection of all population groups, Arctic research and policies must systematically integrate sex- and culture-sensitive perspectives into pollution and health strategies.

Once regarded as pristine, the Arctic regions receive a steady influx of chemical contaminants including heavy metals and persistent organic pollutants (POPs). Although industrial activity is limited in many parts of this area, resulting in fewer local pollution sources, contaminants generated in distant regions are carried over thousands of kilometers via atmospheric circulation and ocean currents and reach the Arctic. At the same time, local pressures are increasing due to intensified human activity, including resource extraction, shipping, and tourism, resulting in additional sources of pollution (Muir et al., 2025). Raising temperatures driven by climate change are exacerbating the problem: long-banned contaminants such as dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), once trapped in glacier surfaces, ice caps or permafrost, are being released and re-entering ecosystems (Ma et al., 2011; Rantanen et al., 2022). As a result, the Arctic is both a receptor and amplifier of global pollution, including emerging and legacy contaminants that pose renewed long-term exposure risks for both wildlife and local populations.

Some of these contaminants bioaccumulate at extremely high levels in the adipose tissue and organs of Arctic wildlife, including in animals

commonly consumed as part of the traditional diets of some local populations (Sonne et al., 2023). Animals at the top of the food chain (e.g., seal), as well as fish and seafood, are known to accumulate extremely high levels of pollutants due to bioaccumulation and/or biomagnification, and their consumption may lead to increased dietary exposure to POPs such as DDT or polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), or inorganic trace elements (e.g. mercury) (Bravo et al., 2019; Abass et al., 2022). Yet, these animals are important sources of proteins and micronutrients and often surpass the nutritional value of store-bought foods, which makes them central to food security and food sovereignty in Arctic communities. They are integral to cultural practices and identity, and access to them is recognized as part of Indigenous Peoples' collective rights under the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) (United Nations. United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples United Nations., 2007). This duality observed in certain food sources is referred to as the "Arctic dilemma", i.e. the policy challenge of ensuring consumer safety while also supporting Indigenous rights and knowledge, preserving social

Abbreviations: DDE, dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene; DDT, dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane; FTS, fluorotelomer sulfonate; OCP, organochlorine pesticide; HCB, hexachlorobenzene; HCH, hexachlorocyclohexane; PCB, polychlorinated biphenyl; PFAS, per- or polyfluoroalkyl substance; PFBA, perfluorobutanoic acid; PFBS, perfluorobutanesulfonic acid; PFDA, perfluorodecanoic acid; PFDoDA, perfluorododecanoic acid; PFDS, perfluorodecanesulfonic acid; PFHpA, perfluoroheptanoic acid; PFHpS, perfluoroheptanesulfonic acid; PFHxA, perfluorohexanoic acid; PFHxDA, perfluorohexadecanoic acid; PFHxS, perfluorohexanesulfonic acid; PFNA, perfluorononanoic acid; PFODA, perfluorooctadecanoate; PFOA, perfluorooctanoic acid; PFOS, perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; PFOSA, perfluorooctanesulfonamide; PFPeA, perfluoropentanoic acid; PFPeS, perfluoropentanesulfonic acid; PFTeDA, perfluorotetradecanoic acid; PFTrDA, perfluorotridecanoic acid; PFUnDA, perfluoroundecanoic acid.

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well-being, and sustaining cultural and spiritual practices (Schäbel et al., 2017).

Recent biomonitoring studies of Arctic populations have revealed a clear trend in the levels of organic contaminants such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), or per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in human blood. Regardless of the chemical class of the substances concerned, women exhibit consistently lower levels (Table 1 and Fig. 1), with average concentrations 26 % lower than those reported in men of the same age groups. At the level of individual compounds, the picture can be more variable, with some substances showing similar levels in both sexes or higher concentrations in women: for example, in 2011, PCB 118 concentrations in blood samples from women in a Russian Arctic community were reported to be 52 % higher than those measured in men (Rylander et al., 2011). However, an overall pattern emerges when considering the summed concentrations of all analytes from each chemical family: in the previous example, the total PCB concentration (considering the 14 congeners included in the analysis) was 23 % lower in women (Rylander et al., 2011). It should be noted that this pattern was only observed for organic contaminants: studies examining trace elements often report heterogeneous results, with no consistent sex-related trends (Ratelle et al., 2018; Skinner et al., 2024).

This recurring pattern appears to stem from two mechanisms: (i) women's initial exposure is lower than men's, and (ii) once the chemical contaminants have entered the body, they follow different metabolic pathways. Although Arctic populations are experiencing a transition towards a reduced consumption of traditional food items (and therefore a lower exposure to chemical contaminants), women are more prone to adapt to these new dietary habits (Aker et al., 2024). Additionally, in many Arctic communities, the consumption of country foods may follow social norms that influence which species, tissues, or portions of animals are preferentially consumed by men or women, as well as the quantities consumed and the contexts in which these foods are shared (Beaumier et al., 2015; Mead et al., 2010). Such patterns may affect both nutritional intake and contaminant exposure, since the distribution of micro-nutrients and contaminants can vary considerably among different tissues of animals commonly consumed in traditional diets. For example, in Nunavik, beluga whale plays an important role in local food traditions, and during the "Women's feast" women commonly consume the tail of the animal, which is known to contain selenoneine, a selenium-containing compound with potential nutritional benefits (Little et al., 2023).

Women also possess unique physiological and metabolic mechanisms during specific stages of their lives (e.g. menstruation, pregnancy, or breastfeeding) that facilitate the excretion of contaminants and reduce their potential bioaccumulation (Shawahna et al., 2018). Despite these factors, the mechanisms underlying sex-related differences in bioaccumulation remain complex and are still not fully understood: some studies have shown that while concentrations increase with age in both sexes, this increase can occur more rapidly in women, so that in older age groups certain compounds may reach higher blood concentrations than in men (Aker et al., 2023).

However, lower levels do not always mean lower risk. The health implications of exposure to organic contaminants are still not fully understood, with documented and suspected effects including endocrine disruption, reproductive harm, neurodevelopmental disorders in children, or increased cancer risks, and women's bodies may respond differently to these chemical exposures, especially during sensitive periods like pregnancy. As an example, a study by Byrne et al. suggested that women may be more susceptible to PFAS-induced thyroid disruption than men, and therefore even a lower exposure or blood burden could result in similar toxicological effects (Byrne et al., 2018).

In the scientific literature, roughly half of the studies reporting human contaminant biomonitoring or risk assessment in Arctic communities involve both men and women (although a percentage of these studies do not report gender- or sex-disaggregated data). Among the

Table 1

Concentration of organic contaminants in blood samples from women and men in Arctic communities.

Chemical Family	Compounds	Sum (women)	Sum (men)	Units	Ref.
PCB	28, 52, 99, 101, 105, 118, 126, 128, 138/163, 149, 153, 156, 169, 170, 180, 183, 187	1959	4319	ng/g lw	(Sandanger et al., 2003)
PCB	99, 101, 105, 118, 128, 138, 153, 156, 170, 180, 183, 187	980	1742	ng/g lw	(Krüger et al., 2012)
PCB	28, 52, 99, 101, 105, 118, 128, 138, 153, 156, 170, 180, 183, 187	143	249	ng/g lw	(Wielsoe et al., 2022)
PCB	28/31, 52, 99, 101, 105, 118, 128, 138, 153, 156, 170, 180, 183, 187	2.2	3.7	µg/L	(Dudarev et al., 2004)
PCB	153	79.0	130	ng/g lw	(Jönsson et al., 2005)
PCB	126, 169	10.5	15.9	pg/L	(Simpson et al., 2019)
PCB	28, 52, 99, 101, 105, 118, 128, 138, 153, 156, 170, 180, 183, 187	1994	2981	ng/g lw	(Deutch et al., 2007)
PCB	28, 52, 99, 101, 105, 118, 128, 138, 153, 156, 170, 180, 183, 187	3287	4669	ng/g lw	(Long et al., 2023)
PCB	118, 138, 153, 156, 170, 180	203	285	ng/g lw	(Nøst et al., 1986)
PCB	28, 52, 99, 101, 105, 118, 128, 138, 153, 156, 170, 180, 183, 187	4.5	6.1	µg/L	(Laird et al., 2013)
PCB	28/31, 52, 99, 101, 105, 110, 118, 138, 153, 156, 170, 180, 187	280	363	ng/g lw	(Rylander et al., 2011)
PCB	99, 118, 138, 146, 153, 156, 163, 170, 178, 180, 183, 187, 194, 201, 203	222	255	ng/g lw	(Aker et al., 2017)
PCB	nd	90.5	100	% diff	(Timmermann et al., 2019)
OCP	DDTs, Chlordane, β-HCH	2482	4691	ng/g lw	(Sandanger et al., 2003)
OCP	Aldrin, α-chlordane, cis-nonachlor, γ-chlordane, HCB, mirex, oxychlordane, p,p'-DDE, p,p'-DDT, β-HCH, trans-nonachlor	192	356	ng/g lw	(Wielsoe et al., 2022)
OCP	cis-chlordane, trans-chlordane, oxychlordane, p,p'-DDE, p,p'-DDT, HCB, β-HCH, mirex, toxaphene 26, toxaphene 50	1471	2505	ng/g lw	(Krüger et al., 2012)
OCP	β-HCH, chlordane, DDTs, HCB, mirex, toxaphene	2004	3308	ng/g lw	(Deutch et al., 2007)
OCP	p,p'-DDT, p,p'-DDE, aldrin, mirex, β-HCH, HCB, cis-nonachlor, trans-nonachlor, α-chlordane,	2572	3918	ng/g lw	(Long et al., 2023)

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Table 1 (continued)

Chemical Family	Compounds	Sum (women)	Sum (men)	Units	Ref.
OCP	γ -chlordanane, oxychlordanane, p,p'-DDE	240	340	ng/g lw	(Jönsson et al., 2005)
OCP	Oxichlordanane, trans-nonachlor, HCB, p,p'-DDE, mirex	444	611	ng/g lw	(Byrne et al., 2015)
OCP	Chlordane, DDTs, toxaphene	5.7	6.7	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Laird et al., 2013)
OCP	HCB, p,p'-DDE, trans-nonachlor	262	290	ng/g lw	(Rylander et al., 2011)
OCP	DDTs, HCH	3.7	3.8	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Dudarev et al., 2004)
OCP	HCB, p,p'-DDE, p,p'-DDT, β -HCH, oxychlordanane, trans-nonachlor	243	232	ng/g lw	(Nøst et al., 1986)
OCP	cis-chlordanane, trans-chlordanane, oxychlordanane, p,p'-DDE, β -HCH, HCB, mirex, toxaphene 26, toxaphene 50	373	340	ng/g lw	(Aker et al., 2017)
PFAS	PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFOSA, PFDS, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTrDA, PFTeDA	9.4	16.3	ng/g lw	(Wielsøe et al., 2022)
PFAS	PFNA, PFOA, PFOS, PFUnDA	7.0	12.0	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Byrne et al., 2018)
PFAS	PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFOSA, PFDS, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTrDA, PFTeDA	83.4	130	ng/g lw	(Long et al., 2023)
PFAS	PFBS, PFPeS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFDS, PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTrDA, PFTeDA, PFHxDA, PFODA, PFOSA, 4:2 FTS, 6:2 FTS, 8:2 FTS	24.8	38.5	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Berg et al., 2021)
PFAS	PFDA, PFHxS, PFNA, PFOA, PFOS, PFUnDA	3.5	5.3	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Garcia-Barrios et al., 2021)
PFAS	PFOS	16.8	20.4	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Château-Degat et al., 2010)
PFAS	PFOS	63.0	71.0	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Dallaire et al., 2009)
PFAS	PFHxS, PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA	94.6	100	% diff	(Timmermann et al., 2019)
PFAS	PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFHxS, PFOS	11.4	12.0	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Aker et al., 2023)
PFAS	PFBS, PFPS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFNS, PFDS, PFDoDS, PFOSA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTrDA, PFTeDA	10.6	10.8	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Averina et al., 2018)

Table 1 (continued)

Chemical Family	Compounds	Sum (women)	Sum (men)	Units	Ref.
PFAS	PFOA, PFHxS, PFOS, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA	12.0	12.1	$\mu\text{g/L}$	(Aker et al., 2017)

remaining studies, most focus exclusively on individuals assigned female at birth. Hence, the concern of the scientific community about women's vulnerabilities to contaminant exposure has inadvertently led to an underrepresentation of men in human biomonitoring studies. The lack of sex-disaggregated data within individual research works, combined with the scarce literature available on men exposure and risk assessment, constrains our understanding of how bioaccumulation and health effects may differ across sexes.

Without a thorough knowledge of how the potential health effects of exposure to contaminants may vary between sexes in the Arctic, policies aiming to ensure the health of the local population may fail to reach those most at risk from specific chemical threats. Currently, local initiatives in the Arctic are usually designed without fully accounting for gender- or sex-driven differences in exposure and vulnerability, and may therefore overlook other segments of the population who are also facing health risks. Thorough and systematic research is needed to avoid relying on generic assumptions, and to ensure that those more at risk from a given health threat are adequately prioritized by local policies.

The complex situation in the Arctic prevents health authorities from making simple, uniform recommendations. Scientific research, policies, and risk communication strategies on chemical exposure should address all population groups affected by a specific chemical threat, taking into account both health risks and dietary patterns. For their part, local initiatives are expected to balance several interconnected dimensions simultaneously, including:

- Food safety, by minimizing the population's exposure to chemical contaminants.
- Food security, by ensuring that policies do not create difficulties in accessing food resources.
- Food adequacy, by promoting nutrient-rich foods.
- Cultural and spiritual identity, by protecting traditional practices that shape a sense of community belonging.

Efforts to reduce exposure to contaminants must also reflect the different ways in which each sex is exposed to and processes pollutants. Men and women experience distinct exposure patterns: they interact differently with their environment, consume different foods, and metabolize contaminants in distinct ways, which affects both the level of exposure and the resulting health consequences. To be effective, policies must be (i) based on sex-sensitive data, (ii) developed in collaboration with Arctic communities to ensure decision-making processes reflect local realities, vulnerabilities, and needs in a culturally appropriate way, and (iii) recognize Indigenous rights, knowledge and participation in decision-making in line with UNDRIP and the 2022 Stockholm + 50 Indigenous Peoples Declaration (United Nations Environment Programme, 2022). The present manuscript therefore calls for coordinated action to strengthen the integration of sex and cultural dimensions into Arctic research and policies addressing persistent contaminants and pollution in general (Fig. 2). In this context, initiatives such as the Women of the Arctic (WoA) association or recent research projects such as the EU-funded ICEBERG project mobilize inclusive approaches and partner with communities to design impactful, sex-inclusive pollution-control strategies. The Arctic is a sentinel of global change and a mirror of global inequities: only inclusive policies based on scientific evidence can help support a resilient and equitable future.

Fig. 1. Concentration ratios of organic contaminants in blood samples from women relative to men for PCBs, OCPs, and PFAS, based on biomonitoring data reported in Arctic populations. Each ratio has been calculated from the summed concentrations of compounds belonging to a given contaminant family in a single dataset. Additional details on the compounds included and the original studies are provided in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Gendered pathways of exposure and bioaccumulation in the Arctic and associated policy challenges.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Gaud Dervilly reports financial support was provided by European Union. The other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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